

A learning-by-demonstration approach for fruit robot-based selective harvesting

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Abstract—This paper presents a robotic platform for fruit selective harvesting that integrates i) an intelligent module for fruit detection and ripeness classification based on multi-spectral sensing and ii) a DMP-based motion planner for fruit picking and placing into a basket through a robotic manipulator. Experimental validation of the proposed platform was conducted on the Tiago robot which, equipped with a 7-DoF robotic arm, an RGB-D camera and a VIS-NIR multispectral device, was trained to classify six tomato ripeness stages and operated to harvest tomatoes placed at 9 different target positions. The results demonstrated the high capability of the proposed platform to evaluate the different ripeness levels (average classification accuracy of 93.72%) and to generalize its motion with respect to different targets (maximum achieved position and orientation error are 8 mm and 0.09 rad, respectively).

Index Terms—Agricultural Robotics, Selective Harvesting, Robot Motion planning, Multi-spectral Sensor

I. INTRODUCTION

Robots can be efficiently employed in agricultural applications to perform repetitive activities that are exhausting for the farmers, such as fruit harvesting [1], which exposes them to unsafe working conditions and long-term work-related diseases. Achieving efficient and accurate selective harvesting requires overcoming many challenges in the agricultural domain including the ability to i) recognize fruits to be harvested and identify their location on the plants ii) assess their ripeness stage, and iii) plan the robot motion while managing the variability of the agricultural environment [2]. This paper presents a robotic platform that integrates an intelligent fruit

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selection module based on multispectral sensing and a human-like motion planner based on Dynamic Motion Primitives (DMPs) [3]. The multi-spectral sensing module, which includes an RGB camera and VIS-NIR multi-spectral sensors [4], provides detailed spectral information about the crops enabling the robot to accurately detect and classify product ripeness through machine learning algorithms, i.e. ReliefF and Support Vector Machine (SVM). The integration of DMPs allows the robotic platform to adapt its motion to different crop types and environmental conditions while performing the activity in a safe and human-like manner [3]. Experimental validation of the proposed platform was conducted on the Tiago robot for 9 target positions to be reached and six tomato ripeness stages to be classified.

II. THE PROPOSED PLATFORM FOR FRUIT SELECTIVE HARVESTING

A block scheme of the proposed robotic platform is shown in Fig. 1. It consists of two main modules, i.e. an intelligent fruit selection module and a DMP-based motion planner, whose description is provided in the following.

Fig. 1. Block scheme of the proposed robotic platform for selective harvesting

A. The intelligent fruit selection module

The intelligent fruit selection module consists of i) a fruit detection and pose estimation module based on RGB-D camera and ii) a fruit ripeness classification module based on a VIS-NIR multi-spectral device. The fruit detection and pose estimation is obtained through a modified Yolov3 neural network which receives images from the RGB camera (i.e. Astra RGB-D camera, manufactured by Orbecc) as input and provides the fruit pose as output. Conversely, the recognition of the different fruit ripeness stages is obtained through intelligent algorithms, which include automatic feature selection and predictive classification models. Automatic feature selection is performed by the ReliefF approach, which analyzes the spectral information collected by the multi-spectral device and automatically extracts relevant features associated with fruit ripeness, regardless of the fruit type. These features are then used to train predictive models through supervised learning, i.e. SVM, to recognize different ripeness stages. The multispectral device hardware components include: i) a broadband LED (i.e. SMB1N-BB450 developed by Roithner Lasertechnik GmbH which emits light across a range of 340-1050 nm) and two multispectral sensors (i.e. C12880MA and the C14384MA manufactured by Hamamatsu Photonics, that operate within the visible to near-infrared spectra).

B. The DMP-based motion planner

Learning by Demonstration based on DMPs consists of two phases. In the first phase, namely the *offline task learning*, trajectories executed by a demonstrator are recorded during the execution of the task, i.e. the human demonstrator manually moves the robotic arm by means of a hands-on approach and the position sensors embedded into the arm are used to record the joint motion. Then, DMP parameters are subsequently extracted from these trajectories using a Locally Weight Regression algorithm (LWR). In the second phase, i.e. the *online task performing*, depending on the sub-task to be performed and on the target position to be reached, an online extraction of the DMP parameters from the dataset is performed by means of a lookup table method and DMPs are subsequently computed for each Cartesian DoF, as a sum of Gaussian kernels weighted by the previously computed parameters, and finally, given as input for the robot position control.

III. EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION

A. Fruit selection: validation and results

The fruit selection module has been experimentally validated on tomatoes, which are among the most consumed fruits worldwide. A total of 450 VIS-NIR spectral measurements were collected from tomatoes at different ripeness stages, namely, Green Mature (GM), Breaker (B), Turning (T), Pink (P), Light Red (LR), and Red-Ripe (RR). Afterwards, a database was built from multispectral signals, and supervised learning methods (i.e. SVM) were trained and tested on the collected database. The resulting accuracy of the proposed approach in identifying the six different tomato ripeness stages is: 94.29% for GM, 90.00% for B, 88.24% for T, 85.00% for P, 86.67% for LR and 97.17% for RR.

B. Motion planner: validation and results

The experimental validation of the motion planner consisted of two phases. In the 1st phase a human subject was asked to teach the robot how to perform the harvesting task, by means of a hands-on approach for four different positions of the targets (i.e. the corner ones shown in Fig. 2) and DMP parameters were computed and stored in a database. In the 2nd phase the robot was operated to perform the same task for the 9 different target positions, shown in Fig. 2, using the previously built database. Hence, performance indicators, i.e. Target Position Error (TPE) and Target Orientation Error (TOE), were calculated on the obtained DMPs to evaluate the approach generalization capability. The achieved results are shown in Fig. 3).

Fig. 2. Target positions to be reached by the robot

Fig. 3. Experimental results for the DMP-based motion planner

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The results demonstrated the high capability of the proposed platform to evaluate the different ripeness levels (average classification accuracy of 93.72%) and to generalize its motion with respect to different targets (maximum achieved position and orientation error are 8 mm and 0.09 rad, respectively).

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